

A popular trend in the development of society, contributing to the provision of a healthy diet, preserving the environment, minimizing harmful emissions, is the focus on the production and consumption of organic products. A common way to confirm the organic properties of certain products is to certify their production and circulation. Production and export of organic products is largely realized at the expense of the countries of Eastern Europe, where the volume of areas suitable for organic production exceeds 3%. The military aggression of the Russian Federation has become a threat to environmental and economic security, a challenge to the global system of food supply, environmental well-being. To preserve the environment and restore the economy, organic production is important, ensuring its certification in accordance with generally accepted standards. The object of this study is the certification of organic production and circulation of organic products. The importance of certification in enabling the effective work of organic market participants is analyzed. The would-be branches of organic production, the mechanism, the main stages, the features of its implementation, as well as the results, have been established. The analysis of the main standards for compliance with which certification of production and circulation of organic products was carried out. Certification bodies that have the right to issue inspection certificates for export to the EU have been identified. It was established that certification of organic production greatly contributes to the practical provision of environmental conservation, guaranteeing minimization of the level of use of synthetic, harmful substances and their emissions, stimulating participants in the agricultural business to be more attentive to the preservation of the environment and natural resources

Keywords: certification, organic products, organic farming, environmental conservation, agricultural ecosystems

ENSURING ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND ECONOMIC RENEWAL THROUGH ORGANIC PRODUCTION CERTIFICATION

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1. Introduction

A globally recognized document, the purpose of which is to protect the planet, ensure peace and well-being of all

people in the world, was adopted on 25.09.2015 by the UN General Assembly, "Agenda for Sustainable Development until 2030" [1]. Of key importance in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals defined by this act are measures

that can be implemented in the process of production and consumption of organic products. This is especially true for enabling proper conditions for ensuring healthy responsible consumption, clean water, proper sanitary conditions, combating climate change, and preserving land ecosystems.

One of the trends that have gained wide popularity both at the global and national levels of many countries is the focus on healthy eating, preserving the environment. Among the components of the implementation of these initiatives, including taking into consideration the principles of social responsibility, care for future generations, considerable attention is paid to the production and consumption of organic products. The products of this assortment group are characterized by a significantly lower content of chemically synthesized compounds, in particular many mineral fertilizers, stimulants and growth regulators, pesticides, herbicides, antibiotics, genetically modified organisms. Prohibited in their production is the use of additional operations in the technological process, primarily the introduction of artificial colors, flavors and preservatives, the use of ionizing radiation, refining, mineralization, and others. As a result, such products are characterized by an improved level of safety and nutritional quality. One of the main means of confirming the fact that certain products are organic is to certify the process of their cultivation or manufacture. With a positive result, it involves the issuance of a provided supporting document, the right to label with a special logo, entering information about the relevant market operator into the registers determined at the state level, recognized at the international level [2].

Since the end of the twentieth century, the production of these products is characterized by significant volumes, and a significant part of them is exported abroad, enabling the preservation of natural ecosystems and quite significant foreign exchange earnings [3, 4]. In 2022, as a result of the military aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, a rather significant reduction in the pace of production of these products and, as a result, deterioration of the functioning of this industry is predicted. In addition to the measures of state support for business, one of the means of minimizing environmental and financial losses, enabling the relaunch of the activities of organizations in the field of organic farming is their certification, which determines the tasks of the present study. The results of such work are necessary for practice because they will contribute to the preservation of the environment, the formation of a bona fide business reputation of enterprises in this area, and an increase in economic efficiency of activities.

2. Literature review and problem statement

A fairly significant number of scientific works report studies into the importance of organic production in the system of environmental conservation measures. In particular, the authors of [5] analyzed the role of production and consumption of organic products as an element of qualitative transformation of the economy to ensure sustainable development and preservation of the environment. The cited study focuses on general approaches to the manufacture and use of organic products, their importance, the prospects of application in the system of meeting the needs of a conscious society. However, the authors do not analyze specific measures aimed at assessing the compliance of the production conditions of these products by an independent authorized

party since the focus is on the benefits achieved from their consumption.

Work [6] explores the role and importance of organic products and their production for consumers, farmers, and the planet as a whole, identifies the main priorities in achieving basic environmental priorities and objectives. At the same time, the fact of implementing measures to comply with the proper production conditions of bringing to consumers requires independent confirmation.

In study [7], an analysis of the rationality of organic farming in the system of agricultural activity was carried out, in particular, to prevent contamination of nature with chemical fertilizers and other compounds, to substantiate the effectiveness of the required costs and efforts. However, it is not analyzed how possible measures by which compliance with established norms can be determined, could contribute to enabling the trust of stakeholders since the main emphasis is on proving economic efficiency.

Scientists in [8] investigated the significance and importance of organic forms of agriculture, achieved as a result of reducing the levels of chemical fertilizers and pollution by harmful emissions of agricultural enterprises. Given the environmental focus of the cited work, it has not been studied how an independent assessment of the established requirements for running an organic business will increase the tenacity of consumers, economic efficiency, in particular exports, and attract new partners and customers.

The authors of [9] analyzed the impact of the use of organic raw ingredients, the introduction of appropriate approaches in the technological processes of organic food production at food industry enterprises and restaurant business establishments. It was established that these measures greatly contributed to minimizing the negative impact on the environment, increasing the social responsibility of organizations in the agricultural sector in the context of environmental initiatives. However, due to the focus of the cited work on the economic field, the question of practical confirmation of a certain type of activity to the established requirements of the norms was not investigated.

Study [10] analyzes modern aspects of enabling the necessary conditions for the functioning of the organic market in the system of environmental initiatives. At the same time, based on the marketing direction of the cited work, the scientific study of the procedure for evaluating the activities in the examined area by the authorized body, the expected advantages were not carried out. Researchers in [11] analyzed statistical data on the functioning of organic business in the world and Romania, characterized the features of certification of organic products. The reported results relate mainly to the Romanian national system and, therefore, further analysis requires advanced international practices in this area.

Worth noting is work [12], which explores the aspects related to the certification of organic products, the prospects for its implementation to ensure the development of the agricultural sector of the Indian economy, export promotion. This study analyzes the algorithm of certification of organic products provided by the regulatory base of India, the peculiarities of its implementation at different stages of the life cycle of products, in particular the main plant crops. However, taking into consideration regional peculiarities, the realities of enabling proper conditions for organic production, in particular their certification, for eastern European countries remain insufficiently investigated.

The activities of organizations in the field of organic production, enabling the circulation of organic products are an important and promising direction of business development, which makes it possible to preserve the environment and obtain economic profit. Certification of the activities of organizations working in this field is an important component of their work, which will make it possible to guarantee compliance with proper economic conditions, the formation of a bona fide business reputation, contribute to the preservation of the environment, proper protection of the rights of target consumers, restoration of economic potential, in particular by attracting new customers and partners, the implementation of export opportunities.

3. Literature review and problem statement

The purpose of this study is to analyze the essence, certification procedures for organic production, the activities of the bodies authorized to carry it out, the measures of state support determined for this purpose. This is necessary to ensure the rights of consumers, preserve the environment, and restore the economy, in particular, by creating favorable conditions for the competitive work of organizations working in the field of organic farming and establishing exports.

To accomplish the aim, the following tasks have been set:

- to study the state of the organic market;
- to analyze the legislative and regulatory support for certification of organic production, its main content, and measures of state support in this area;
- to determine the internationally accredited bodies authorized to carry out certification of organic production, and main directions of their activities.

4. The study materials and methods

The object of this study was organic production and circulation of organic products.

The hypothesis of the study assumed that certification of organic production will ensure the preservation of the environment and economic recovery.

As a methodological basis for the study, the current legislative and regulatory framework for enabling certification of organic production and circulation of organic products in Ukraine was applied. Open information, reference, and statistical data and information on the state of production and consumption of organic products, internationally accredited bodies authorized to carry it out in Ukraine, the activities of the organization Organic Standard LLC (Ukraine) were used.

During our research, the methods of scientific analysis and synthesis, isolation and generalization, comparison, induction and deduction, systematization of approaches to certification in the field of organic business were applied.

5. The results of research on the meaning, essence, legislative and regulatory support, aspects of certification of organic production

5.1. The results of research on the state of the organic market

It has been investigated that at the present stage of human development, the culture of consumption of organ-

ic products in the world, in particular at the level of EU countries, is characterized by a significant pace of development and gaining popularity. According to the results of the 2020/2021 marketing year (MY), the share of these products in the structure of food consumption amounted to about 1.5 %, in particular in the USA and Western Europe an countries it exceeded 4 % [6–8]. Currently, the production of organic goods is carried out in almost 190 countries of the world, more than 3.5 million people of the population and 73 million hectares of total areas are involved in this area of the economy [13–15]. The level of demand for organic products in many countries, including the USA and the EU, significantly exceeds the corresponding supply indicator, which opens up significant opportunities for export and supply from other countries [14, 15]. Taking into consideration the compliance of the legislative framework for certification of organic production with similar ones in the world, in particular the EU, the USA, Ukrainian products of this group can enter the world market without technical restrictions.

Due to the available resource of organic areas of about 460 thousand ha, favorable weather conditions, available labor resources, favorable geographical location Ukraine has significant potential for the production and marketing of organic products [16, 17]. This is confirmed by the fact that in terms of exports of these products in 2019, it became No. 2 in the world, in 2018 and 2020 – 4th, thus enabling the supply of more than 24 categories of products.

It is appropriate to note that the export of Ukrainian organic products is focused mainly on European countries, where in 2020 almost 73 % of these products were sent [16, 17].

In 2020, 217.2 thousand tons were exported to the EU countries of Ukrainian organic agricultural products worth approximately USD 117 million [4, 17]. Also, that year, Ukraine sold almost 332 thousand tons of organic products to about 40 countries of the world, providing income at the level of USD 204 million [4]. The main importing countries were the Netherlands, USA, Germany, China, Great Britain, Canada, Japan, Austria, Lithuania, Poland, Italy, Switzerland. The main export products supplied to international markets were cereals, oilseeds, honey, eggs, vegetables and fruits, sunflower cake, flour, sunflower oil, apple concentrate and birch sap. In total, about 80 items of organic goods were exported by Ukraine. Such success, in particular technical access to these markets, was largely ensured by the certification of Ukrainian organic products in accordance with international generally accepted standards.

The military attack of the Russian Federation has significantly reduced the level of organic business in Ukraine in MY 2022/2023. Thus, the beginning of the sowing campaign of these products took place under difficult conditions, in particular due to rocket strikes, the need to recover from the occupation and destruction, active hostilities in Donetsk, Zaporizhia, Mykolaiv, Kharkiv, Kherson oblasts. It should also be noted that due to the military events in the Luhansk oblast, crops did not start at all. Because of the military operations, a certain part of workers who were supposed to be involved in the preparation and conducting of crop activities in organic areas partially left their places of residence and work, were involved in defense activities, volunteer actions, and accommodation of refugees.

To ensure the preservation of the ecology of economic recovery, obtaining the resources and financial resources nec-

essary for the victory of the Ukrainian army, and preserving the Ukrainian sector of organic farming, it is necessary to apply the maximum range of measures. One of such means that will additionally be able to ensure compliance with the requirements of the legislative and regulatory framework of importing countries, the trust of stakeholders, in particular consumers and partners, traceability of the trade route, is certification of production and circulation of organic products.

5. 2. Results of examining the legislative and regulatory support for certification of organic production, the content and measures of state support

It is established that the legal term “certification of organic production and/or circulation of organic products” is defined by the current Law of Ukraine “On basic principles and requirements for organic production, circulation, and labeling of organic products” [2]. It is the verification and establishment of compliance of production and/or circulation of products with the requirements of legislation in the field of organic production, circulation, and labeling of organic products.

The main regulations in the field of certification of organic production are:

- Law of Ukraine “On basic principles and requirements for organic production, circulation and labeling of organic products” [2].

- Law of Ukraine “On State Support of Agriculture of Ukraine” [18].

- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine “On Approval of the Procedure for Certification of Organic Production and/or Circulation of Organic Products” [19].

- Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine “On approval of the Procedure for maintaining the State Register of Operators engaged in production in accordance with the requirements of legislation in the field of organic production, circulation, and labeling of organic products, the State Register of Certification Bodies in the Field of Organic Production and Circulation of Organic Products, the State Register of Organic Seeds and Planting Material” [20].

- Order of the Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine “On approval of the state logo for organic products” [21], and others.

According to Ukrainian legislation [2], it is defined that organic production is a certified activity related to the production of agricultural products at all stages of the technological process, carried out in compliance with the requirements of the law. These stages include primary production (including harvesting), preparation, processing, mixing, and related procedures, filling, packaging, processing, restoration, and other changes in the state of products. Certification branches of organic production are organic crop production (seed production, seedling), animal husbandry (poultry farming, beekeeping), mushroom growing (in particular, the cultivation of organic yeast), aquaculture, production of seaweed, food products. In particular, the types of organic production of food products are organic winemaking, the manufacture of organic feed, the harvesting of organic objects of the plant world. In Ukraine, certification of the activities of organic market operators is carried out by bodies included in the special Register, in accordance with Ukrainian legislation, and institutions from the List of foreign certification bodies in accordance with the norms of other state administrations [2].

According to the provisions of the Ukrainian legislation [2, 19], in order to acquire the status of an organic market operator, a certain entity must submit an application for certification signed by an authorized person. The result of this is the conclusion of an appropriate agreement with a specific certification body and the payment for these services. This body then submits to the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine an application for the inclusion of a certain legal entity in the Register of Operators, which is carried out within 10 days. On the basis of the concluded agreement with a certain applicant, the certification body attaches it to the annual inspection plan, determines their terms and form, in particular the first, which is the basis for establishing a transition period, and a planned one. It is worth noting that during the first inspection at all stages of production and circulation, soil, certain materials, or products for research are selected, the necessary basic and, in the case of import of products, additional information is provided. Based on the results of work carried out, the certification body prepares the predicted certificate on the day of completion of the inspection. The inspector of the relevant branch of organic production and/or circulation of organic products based on this document, taking into consideration the information provided by the operator, evaluates the work, and draws up a report, which is also sent to the applicant. It was established that the regulatory framework [19] provides for the first inspection up to 10 working days. At the same time, the analysis of the practical experience of Organic Standard LLC accredited for organic certification [22] shows that the duration of this process in most cases is 6–8 days.

Based on the generated report, a decision is made to issue or refuse to issue a certificate, the validity period of which is 15 months. During this period, the certification body must ensure the implementation of supervisory audits to confirm and ensure a previously established fact. In addition, the legislation [19] determines that when carrying out the relevant actions, the certification body determines the compliance of all stages of production and/or circulation of products with current standards. This is done by conducting the first inspection and determining the start date of the transition period (if applicable), conducting subsequent inspections, monitoring, and certification support of the operator Ukrainian’s business activities. It is pertinent to note that the Ukrainian base for certification of organic production is developed on the basis of the norms and recommendations of the International Federation of Organic Agricultural Movement (IFOAM) and corresponds to the same one in force in the EU, USA.

It should also be noted that in accordance with the Law of Ukraine “On State Support of Agriculture of Ukraine” [18], in particular Article 17.9, it provides for the possibility of state financing of the organic sector in Ukraine. This legislative act stipulates that state support for producers of organic agricultural products is carried out by:

- allocation of budget subsidies per unit of cultivated land and/or one head of cattle;

- reimbursement of up to 30 % of the cost of certification of organic production;

- reimbursement of up to 30 % of the cost of purchasing permitted plant protection products and fertilizers, seeds, planting material, and feed.

It was investigated that the 2021 budget did not provide enough funds to provide state support to organic

producers, in particular to reimburse the cost of certification services. It is also important to note that despite the provisions provided for by the Law [18], there is currently no defined “Procedure for the distribution and use of funds in the direction of organic production” [23]. It was also established that the relevant order of the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine has not yet been adopted to implement the envisaged measures of state support. As a result, boards have not been established at the regional level to form lists of recipients of financial support, and in some regions, there are no relevant programs at the local level. In addition, catastrophic consequences for the activities of Ukrainian organizations operating in the field of production and circulation of organic products, in particular their certification, were caused by a military attack by the Russian Federation.

The review of data [22, 24, 25] on the basic standards for compliance with which certification of organic production and products is carried out allows us to state that in general it is possible to distinguish their following main groups:

– fundamental international ones define the generally accepted requirements for organic products, in particular their production, the use of reproductive material for obtaining, controlling the circulation, trade and certification process. They are the “General Goals and Requirements of Organic Standards” (COROS) of the International Federation of Organic Agricultural Movement (IFOAM), the standard of the Commission Codex Alimentarius for organically produced food products,

Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council (EU) No. 2018/848;

– national ones were developed in accordance with generally accepted international ones and define the requirements for organic products and their production at the national level. Their examples are the U.S. Department of Agriculture’s National Organic Program (USDA/NOP), Swiss Organic Regulation, Japanese Agricultural Standard (JAS), and others;

– private ones establish higher ones, rather than generally accepted requirements and norms for organic products. They are focused on sales in a particular market. These include Demeter (used globally), Soil Association (UK), Naturland, Ecovin, and Ecoland (Germany), KRAV (Sweden), BioSuisse (Switzerland), BIOlan (Ukraine), and others.

5.3. Results of studying the activities of internationally accredited bodies authorized to carry out certification of organic production, and the main directions of their activities

It was established that 20 internationally accredited certification bodies recognized by the European Commission for the provision of control services for organic production and circulation of organic products have been identified in the EU (Table 1) [26]. It is envisaged that according to the results of the certification, they have the right to issue inspection certificates for the export of organic products to the EU.

Table 1

Internationally accredited certification bodies recognized by the European Commission (organic production and circulation of organic products)

No.	Certification authority code	Certification authority name	Country	Intended areas of certification*					
				A	B	C	D	E	F
1	UA-BIO-108	Organic Standard	Ukraine	+	+	+	+	+	+
2	UA-BIO-102	Control and Certification of Organic Products (CCPB Sr)	Italy	+	+	–	+	+	–
3	UA-BIO-112	Ecoglobe	Armenia	+	+	–	+	–	–
4	UA-BIO-115	Ethical and Environmental Certification Institute (ICEA)	Italy	+	–	–	+	–	–
5	UA-BIO-132	Bioagricert S.r.l	Italy	+	+	–	+	–	–
6	UA-BIO-134	Lacon GmbH	Germany	–	–	–	–	–	–
7	UA-BIO-135	Letis S.A	Argentina	+	–	+	+	–	–
8	UA-BIO-139	Albinspekt	Albania	–	+	–	–	–	–
9	UA-BIO-140	CERES Certification of Environmental Standards GmbH	Germany	+	+	–	+	–	–
10	UA-BIO-141	Kiwa BCS Öko-Garantie GmbH	Germany	+	–	–	+	+	–
11	UA-BIO-149	Control Union Certifications	Netherlands	+	+	+	+	+	+
12	UA-BIO-150	Suolo e Salute srl	Italy	+	–	–	–	–	–
13	UA-BIO-151	Agreco R.F Göderz GmbH	Germany	+	+	–	+	–	–
14	UA-BIO-154	Ecocert SA	France	+	+	–	+	+	–
15	UA-BIO-161	Bio.inspecta AG	Switzerland	+	+	–	+	+	+
16	UA-BIO-171	A CERT European Organization for Certification S.A	Greece	+	–	–	+	–	–
17	UA-BIO-173	SIA “Sertifikācijas un testēšanas centrs”	Latvia	+	+	–	+	+	+
18	UA-BIO-177	Biocert International Pvt Ltd	Poland	+	–	–	+	+	–
19	UA-BIO-181	DQS Polska sp. z o.o.	Poland	+	+	–	+	–	–
20	UA-BIO-110	Organización Internacional Agropecuaria	Argentina	+	–	–	+	–	–

Note: *Product categories: A – crop products that have not been processed; B – live animals or livestock products that have not been processed; C – aquaculture products and algae; D – processed products of agricultural origin for consumption as food; E – products of processing of agricultural origin for use as feed; F – planting material and seeds.

Among the certification bodies recognized by the European Commission in the field of organic activity, the Ukrainian organization Organic Standard LLC is represented. As a result of the analysis of [22, 24], it was found that during 2021 the majority of organic operators in Ukraine ensured the export of their products through certificates issued by Organic Standard LLC. As a result, more than 75 % of Ukrainian organic operators from Ukraine secured more than 2,700 export shipments.

One example of organizations certified by the international certification body of Organic Standard LLC is GALEKS-AGRO PE company [27]. It is one of the leading exporters of organic products in Ukraine. Certification of this enterprise makes it possible to ensure its effective activity, the main focus of which, in accordance with the charter, is the production of organic certified products. GALEKS-AGRO PE began its work in 2008, when the first 200 hectares of service lands were developed, their certification as an “organic transition period”. In 2010, a dairy commodity complex was also built in the village of Gulsk, Zhytomyr oblast, and product certification by the Institute of Environmental Marketing “IMO” (Switzerland) was ensured.

Since 2011, the company's products began to be introduced to the European market (Switzerland, Germany, the Netherlands), and in 2013, to increase recognition, certification of the main activities by the international certification body Organic Standard LLC was initiated. This, in turn, allowed GALEKS-AGRO PE to reliably provide a certain direction of work, socially responsible reputation, optimize the production process, successfully export its products to Switzerland, Great Britain, Germany, the Netherlands, Hungary, Italy. At the end of 2020, the profit of this organization from the export of products abroad, was about USD 3.2 million. It is worth noting that to a large extent that result was achieved thanks to the certification of Organic Standard LLC, which ensured the entry of products into the international market. It is worth noting that the costs associated with certification by the Ukrainian body amounted to about USD 3200. This, in turn, gives grounds to argue about the economic efficiency of certification of organic production.

6. Discussion of the results of studying the meaning, essence, regulatory support, aspects of certification of organic production

It has been analyzed that the fact that the consumption of organic products is widely spread at the present stage is explained, first of all, by the higher level of orientation towards healthy food. The spread of the coronavirus disease was also an important influencing factor. It is predicted that in the future the practice of production, market circulation, consumption of organic products will steadily develop, gain popularity, and spread.

Based on our analysis of data on the beginning and current state of organic crops, it was found that many Ukrainian producers focused on export products had to reorient themselves to grow other crops. They were, first of all, cereals, fruit and vegetable crops, in particular spring wheat and vegetables. In addition, organic farmers were forced to reconsider the feasibility of activities due to a temporary partial ban and state licensing of food resources exports to ensure food security of the population. At the same time, in order to stimulate the work of business entities, in particular

in the field of organic production, the state has created simplified tax conditions, provided interest-free loans for the purchase of seeds, as well as fuel and lubricants.

The analysis of state support measures in the field of organic production and circulation of these products showed that a set of measures in this area has been determined at the legislative level. In particular, partial reimbursement to organizations of the cost of certification is provided. At the same time, the practical implementation of these measures is not carried out due to the lack of the procedure for distribution and payment of necessary funds determined by the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine, their lack in the State Budget of the state. Thus, in order to create appropriate conditions for doing business in the field of organic production and circulation, including carrying out and the necessary certification, the necessary base of appropriate resources for financing must be provided at the legislative level.

Based on the results of our analysis of the legislative and regulatory framework for certification of organic products, it is determined that as a result of its implementation, producers obtain the opportunity to label their products with the provided signs and logos. These signs and marks indicate organic properties, ensure the interest and trust of new partners, including importers, representatives of retail chains through which the sale will be carried out, and, ultimately, consumers. In Ukraine, a special national logo for organic products is provided for such products. It was also investigated that certification can be carried out for compliance with certain domestic and foreign regulatory requirements, in particular national and private standards.

Based on the data given in Table 1, we established that most of the internationally accredited certification bodies recognized by the European Commission for the provision of organic production control services are European, in particular Italian and German. The only Ukrainian organization is Organic Standard LLC. This organization, which has received accreditation from the International Organic Accreditation Service (IOAS) in accordance with ISO Guide 17065, is currently authorized by the EU to carry out certification in the organic field in all 5 areas of certification, namely:

- crop products that have not been processed;
- live animals or livestock products that have not been processed;
- aquaculture products and algae;
- processed products of agricultural origin for consumption as food;
- products of processing of agricultural origin for use as feed;
- planting material and seeds.

It was found that the services provided by the certification body of Organic Standard LLC make it possible to significantly ensure the export of Ukrainian organic products to the EU and US markets. This is achieved by understanding the specific needs of organic producers in Ukraine and at a relatively low cost (about USD 1000 per type of activity).

The cost of certification services in the field of organic activities provided by the Ukrainian body is significantly lower compared to similar ones determined by other international relevant bodies [4, 22]. It was established that certification of organic production is characterized by a rather low cost compared to the advantages, in particular financial ones, that can be obtained by organizations. It was analyzed and established that the certification of organic production contributes to the preservation of the clean ecological state

of the areas involved in them, the formation and implementation of environmental initiatives among other organizations and citizens. The results of this seminal work are especially important for restoring the ecology of the state and restarting the organic agricultural business.

Limitations of the study include the impossibility of certification of certain existing organic industries due to cases of violation of the organic state of their lands during the hostilities, re-profiling to other activities to maintain profitability.

The development of this study may involve the analysis of the facts of certification of organic production during the period of hostilities and the restoration of Ukraine, the impact on the preservation of the environment, enabling business reputation, economic efficiency of industry enterprises.

7. Conclusions

1. It has been investigated that the market of organic products, especially in the United States, Western Europe, is characterized by high rates of development, due to the focus on a healthy diet and the preservation of the environment. It has been established that in recent years Ukraine has been one of the main producers and exporters of organic products as a result of the presence of a significant amount

of organic agricultural areas. At the same time, a significant decrease in Ukrainian production of these products as a result of a military attack is predicted.

2. Our analysis of the legislative and regulatory support for certification of organic production in Ukraine showed the existence of a clearly defined procedure that is harmonized with the international one. It is determined that its implementation at the legislative level provides for state support but the implementation of these provisions is restrained due to the lack of necessary legislative documents.

3. International accredited bodies authorized to carry out certification of organic production in Ukraine and having the right to issue inspection certificates for the export of organic products have been determined. The main activity is certification of the production and circulation of crop products, live animals or livestock products that have not been processed, products of processing of agricultural origin for consumption.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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